

Technical Note

The Resistor Noise Index – an intuitive reformulation

Relation to measurements and precision limits

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The noise index (NI) of a resistor or resistive sensor is a property that is not commonly regarded as being overly relevant. It is not typically given in component datasheets. However, when one is concerned with precision measurements, the noise index of the device under test is often literally all you need to know! It is absolutely decisive and other properties fade in relevance. One reason why the noise index might not receive the attention it deserves, could be its awkward definitions and resulting unintuitive value. In this technical note, two alternative definitions for the noise index will be presented. Both are easier to relate to measured quantities and they give the precision limit of the resistor or resistive sensor in a direct and intuitive way. The reformulation also highlights the meaning of the noise index for material physics.

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1. Introduction

All resistors generate noise thermally with a spectral power density of $4 \cdot k_B \cdot T$, a direct consequence of statistical physics. When the resistor is connected to an electric circuit or a measurement instrument, this noise can be measured. A voltmeter will detect voltage noise at a spectral density of $\sqrt{4 \cdot k_B \cdot T \cdot R}$, if it is sensitive enough. This spectral density does not depend on the frequency, it is so-called “white” noise akin to white light, which has roughly constant intensity across the visible spectral range. In the context of precision measurements, white noise is rather benign: By including a larger and larger number N of readings in a calculated mean value, one can reduce the expected error in proportion with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}$. As a result, one could achieve arbitrary precision by just taking enough readings.

However, realistic noise is not spectrally white, but its power density rises at low frequencies. That means that the excursions of the noise signal become larger when one considers longer timescales. When averaging longer, one inevitably includes more and more of this noisy low frequency part of the spectrum and this counteracts the noise suppression effect of the longer averaging itself. As a result, even the shallowest increase of noise power density towards low frequencies, the so-called $1/f$ noise or “pink” noise, is enough to completely negate any beneficial effect of further increases in averaging time.

While white noise does not impose a precision limit, $1/f$ noise does. Resistors are no different in this regard – their definable precision is limited due to so-called “excess noise”, a type of current-induced noise with $1/f$ spectral shape. What happens is that when one attempts to measure the value of a resistor, the current flow

through the resistor causes its value to become slightly non-stationary. Figuratively speaking, the probe electrons disturb the electronic structure of the resistor due to material physics. More electrons disturb more and, therefore, one can never know the value of the resistor more precisely than just how much this value becomes disturbed by the probe current. This relation of probe current to disturbance of the resistor itself is what is given by the *noise index* of the resistor. Less disturbance gives a lower noise index and vice versa. The noise index depends mainly on two factors: Material quality and material volume. More metallic and physically larger resistors have a lower noise index than less metallic and smaller resistors with an equal resistance value.

2. Conventional definition

The conventional definition of the noise index¹ is as follows: A noise index of 0 dB means that a resistor generates 1 μ V of RMS noise per spectral decade and per volt applied to the resistor. From this baseline on, other values follow as usual for voltage relations given in dB, i.e. a tenfold increase in noise is equivalent to a 20 dB increase. This definition has a number of issues for both the measurement and its usability.

- a) It applies only to the $1/f$ noise spectral region. But when measuring the noise voltage over time, it is not readily evident whether the signal is dominated by $1/f$ noise or not.
- b) The RMS value shall be calculated while taking into account one spectral decade of the $1/f$ noise. But this would require unreasonably sharp band-pass filters.

¹ "Review on excess noise measurements of resistors", *Sensors* 23(3), 1107, (2023) and references therein, by D. Walter, A. Bülow and A. Zimmermann

- c) The noise index provides no handy relation to the precision limit of the resistor.

3. Relations to the noise spectrum

Due to the issues of its conventional definition mentioned above, the noise index is commonly evaluated via the noise spectrum, usually by taking a portion of time domain noise data and taking their Fourier transform. The spectrum will make it straightforward to identify the spectral range, in which $1/f$ noise is dominant. Moreover, no band-passes are necessary making the acquisition experimentally easy. **Figure 1(a)** shows such spectra of the voltage noise across a resistor at varying levels of drive voltage and hence varying current through the resistor.

One noteworthy feature is that $1/f$ noise rises as the drive voltage is increased. The $1/f$ voltage noise density coefficient $v_{1/f}$, which gives the amplitude of the $1/f$ noise at 1 Hz, is proportional to the drive voltage V_{Drv} , where the proportionality ρ is governed by the noise index.

$$\frac{v_{1/f}}{V_{Drv}} = \rho_{NI} \tag{1}$$

Therefore, one can normalize these curves by the drive voltage to obtain the data shown in **Figure 1(b)** and labeled by the left axis. As resistors have a linear I - V relationship, one can obtain an alternative normalization by dividing by the drive current instead of the drive voltage, yielding resistance noise spectra with a $1/f$ resistance noise density coefficient $r_{1/f}$ instead (right axis). Both normalizations are equivalent and differ only in the additional remaining factor of the base resistance R in the latter case. So to obtain fully equivalent representations, one can either measure the voltage noise and normalize by the drive voltage or measure the resistance noise and normalize by the base resistance value of the resistor.

In any case, one will obtain a $1/\sqrt{f}$ slope region in the noise amplitude spectrum that is governed by the unitless coefficient ρ_{NI} , irrespective of the actual drive voltage or current.

$$\frac{\rho_{NI}}{\sqrt{f}} = \frac{v_{1/f}}{V_{Drv} \cdot \sqrt{f}} = \frac{v_{1/f}}{I_{Drv} \cdot R \cdot \sqrt{f}} = \frac{r_{1/f}}{R \cdot \sqrt{f}} \tag{2}$$

In **Figure 1(b)**, this overarching relation (Eq. 2) is drawn as the bold dashed line and the coefficient ρ_{NI} is given by the value of that line at

Figure 1: (a) Voltage noise spectral density of a 560 Ω resistor in dependence of the voltage applied across it. The applied voltage scales logarithmically from 10 V (topmost cyan line) to 10 mV (bottommost blue line). The $1/f$ contribution is proportional to the drive voltage. (b) Noise spectral density normalized by the drive voltage (left axis) or by drive current (right axis). All curves converge on the bold dashed line indicating the precision floor. In this example, the noise index is -30 dB.

1 Hz. When one does the math, one can derive an exact relationship between the noise index (NI) and the corresponding noise spectrum, which allows expressing the noise index directly using the spectral coefficient p_{NI} .

$$NI = \left(6 + \log_{10} \left(p_{NI} \sqrt{\ln 10} \right) \right) \cdot 20 \text{ dB} \quad \mathbf{3}$$

This relation reveals that a spectral coefficient of $p_{NI} = \frac{1}{10^6 \sqrt{\ln 10}} \approx 6.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$ corresponds to a noise index of 0 dB. The example shown in **Figure 1(b)** reveals a $p_{NI} \approx 2.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$, which is the value of the bold line at 1 Hz. According to Eq. **3**, this value corresponds to a noise index of -30 dB. A single spectrum is thus sufficient to determine p_{NI} and, in turn, the noise index.

4. Relations to the precision limit

As an alternative to the spectral analysis discussed above, we will show next that a time domain analysis of the measured noise can be done directly, to obtain both the noise index and the precision limit associated with the noise index.

For this, we will employ the Allan deviation analysis of the time domain signal. The Allan deviation value of a noise signal states how reproducible measurements are, when done

with a given integration time. For pure white noise signals, the Allan deviation is equivalent to the standard error of the mean, i.e. it will decrease forever as the averaging time τ is increased, in proportion with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{\tau}}$. However, for non-stationary noise signals such as the one shown in **Figure 2(a)**, the standard error fails to provide a robust estimate of the reproducibility. The Allan deviation can be understood as a rigorous generalization of the standard error for general noise signals.

For all non-stationary noise signals, the Allan deviation will eventually reach a minimum or floor when the averaging time exceeds a certain value. At this point, longer averaging times will either no longer improve the precision of the reading or even deteriorate it. For the case of a resistor with $1/f$ excess noise, this relation indicates that it is fundamentally impossible to reproducibly measure the resistor more precisely than the floor of the Allan deviation. **Figure 2(b)** shows the Allan deviation σ_y of the time domain resistance noise signal. The Allan deviation first decreases for longer integration times, before reaching the noise floor region of approximately $14 \mu\Omega$. By putting this value into relation with the base resistance one obtains the

Figure 2: (a) Resistance noise over time of a 560 Ω resistor with a noise index of -30 dB, with 0.6 V applied across the resistor. The non-stationarity due to $1/f$ noise is visible as up and down excursions of the signal. (b) Allan deviation over integration time τ as calculated from the time domain data (black) and theoretical trend for the known white and pink spectral noise densities (grey line).

relative precision limit: $\sigma_{y,\min} = 14 \mu\Omega/560 \Omega \approx 2.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$.

The height of this noise floor $\sigma_{y,\min}$ depends only on the amount of $1/f$ noise for the present case of a resistor with excess noise. Notably, the amount of white noise from the resistor itself or from instrumentation is irrelevant for the precision limit. As the precision limit depends solely on the $1/f$ voltage noise, there is a fixed relation between the $1/f$ voltage noise spectral density coefficient ($p_{NI} \approx 2.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$ as we have seen before) and the precision limit:

$$\sigma_{y,\min} = p_{NI} \sqrt{2 \ln 2} \quad 4$$

This reveals that measuring the relative precision limit via the Allan deviation of the noise signal in the time domain is an equivalent method of determining the noise index of a resistor. Coincidentally, the value p_{NI} is rather close to the rigorous precision limit: approximately $0.85 \cdot \sigma_{y,\min}$. Therefore, both values p_{NI} and $\sigma_{y,\min}$ provide a realistic impression of the attainable precision. Both values convey equivalent information as the noise index, but in a much more intuitive format.

Table 1 provides numerical relations for several noise indices and the rulers in **Figure 3** show the conversion graphically.

Noise index NI	Spectral coefficient p_{NI}	Precision limit $\sigma_{y,\min}$
-40 dB	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$
-20 dB	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-8}$
-6 dB	$3.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-7}$
0 dB	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-7}$
2.2 dB	$8.49 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$
3.6 dB	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-6}$
6 dB	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$
20 dB	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$
40 dB	$6.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$7.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Table 1: Comparative scaling of the conventional definition of the noise index NI , the $1/f$ noise spectral coefficient p_{NI} and the relative precision limit $\sigma_{y,\min}$. The bold values highlight the 0 dB reference values.

Figure 3: Graphical scaling representation of the conventional definition of the noise index (bottom) and the corresponding relative precision limits and $1/f$ noise spectral coefficients. Vertical lines connect equivalent values.

5. Relation to statistical physics

At first glance, the noise index appears to be less deeply related with statistical physics than the thermal (Johnson-Nyquist) noise. However, the reformulations of the noise index in terms of p_{NI} and $\sigma_{y,min}$ add an absolute scale to the excess noise phenomenon. In this context, the common scaling of the excess noise with the conductor volume V becomes important. For a given material the precision limit scales in proportion with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{V}}$. This suggests an extrapolation to a small volume, at which the relative precision limit becomes 1. Such a characteristic conduction volume V_C would be the smallest volume for which conduction becomes statistically significant, which further hints at a relation with the charge carrier concentration. For an isotropic material, one can also propose a corresponding characteristic length scale d_C :

$$V_C = \sigma_{y,min}^2 \cdot V \quad d_C = \sqrt[3]{\sigma_{y,min}^2 \cdot V} \quad 5$$

As an example, for the resistor previously discussed, for an assumed volume of 0.1 mm^3 , one would obtain a characteristic length scale of $d_C = 4.0 \text{ nm}$. This shows the relation of $1/f$ noise to the nanoscale physics of resistive materials.

6. Easy measurement of the noise index

As established above, there are two unitless quantities, the coefficient of the $1/f$ spectral noise density p_{NI} and the relative precision limit $\sigma_{y,min}$, both of which relate intuitively to measurable quantities and both of which are alternative formulations of the resistor noise index. As these quantities are unitless, one is free to choose in which dimension to measure the $1/f$ excess noise of the resistor.

The conventional way is to record the excess voltage noise in relation with the drive voltage.

However, the voltage measurement approach suffers from one important issue: Any $1/f$ noise of the drive voltage will appear also in the noise measurement. While this effect can be attenuated using a Wheatstone bridge, the only way to fully eliminate it, is to constantly measure the drive voltage using the same reference source that is used to measure the noise voltage. This can be achieved with a two-channel voltmeter, but not (easily) with two single-channel voltmeters.

As an alternative, one can measure the resistance noise directly with an integrated ohmmeter, which implicitly measures the drive current. The advantage with this approach is that the resistance reading obtained in such a way is typically immune to $1/f$ noise contributions from the voltage reference. Dedicated knowledge of the drive voltage or current is not necessary as shown by Eq. 2.

AC modulation should be used to further suppress $1/f$ noise of the instrumentation, whenever possible. This can be achieved by either using a two-channel chopping-stabilized voltmeter or, slightly easier, by using a modulated drive signal. An example for a modulated-drive two-channel voltmeter would be most lock-in amplifiers, which are indeed often used for measurements of the noise index. An example for a modulated-drive integrated ohmmeter would be the Tensormeter RTM1 or RTM2 from Tensor Instruments.

In fact, the Tensormeter devices allow for even more extreme instrumentation noise suppression by virtue of their integrated switch matrix. This utility extends all the way to literally total $1/f$ noise suppression of the resistance measurement instrumentation, as will be detailed in a separate Application Note².

² "Beyond the Wheatstone bridge: Extend precision by switching", [Zenodo 11066597](https://zenodo.org/record/11066597), (2024)